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Report of the 3rd Granada Workshop: State of development of WP14 interactions with other HBM4EU-WPs

Additional Deliverable Report AD14.7

WP14 - Effect biomarkers

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Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Received]
Coordinator	Marike Kolossa-Gehring	UBA	21/04/2022
Grant Signatory	Argelia Castaño	ISCI	21/03/2022

Entity	Name of person responsible	Short name institution	Date [Approved]
Pillar Leader	Robert Barouki	INSERM	21/03/2022
Work Package Leader	Mariana F. Fernandez	UGR	15/03/2022
Task Leader	Mariana F. Fernandez	UGR	15/03/2022

Responsible authors	Mariana F. Fernández, Elena Salamanca, Andrea Rodríguez, Vicente Mustieles, Nicolás Olea
Short name of institution	UGR

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Co-authors	<p>Greet Schoeters (VITO), Kirsten Baken (VITO), Eva Govarts (VITO), Argelia Castaño (ISCIIII), Ludek Bláha (MU), Antonio Hernández (EASP), Marina Lacasaña (EASP), Tiina Saantonen (FIOH), Maria João Silva (INSA), Birgitte Lindeman (NIPH), Claudia Gundacker (MUW), Eva Cecilie Bonfeld-Jørgensen (AU), Anna-Maria Andersson (RegionH), Anne-Marie Vinggaard (DTU), Arthur David (INSERM), Shereen Cynthia (INSERM), Katrin Kreuzer (BfR), Jean-Baptiste Fini (CNRS), Jochem Louisse (RIKILT - RIVM), Tessa Schillemans (KI), Anteneh Desalegn (NIPH), Nina Iszatt (NIPH), Sylvie Remy (VITO), Fabio Barbone (EPIUD), Valentina Rosolen (EPIUD), Gudrun Koppen (VITO). <i>HBM4EU chromates study team</i>: Ana Tavares, Célia Ventura, Henriqueta Louro, Sónia Namorado, Kukka Aimonen, Julia Catalan, Simo Porrás, Sophie Ndaw, Aleksandra Fučić, Susana Viegas, Carina Ladeira, Radu Corneliu Duca, An Van Nieuwenhuysse, Wojciech Wasowicz, Paul Scheepers, Ovnair Sepai, Jelle Verdonck, Lode Godderis, Bruno Gomes, Catarina Afonso, Katrien Poels</p>
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Authors and acknowledgements

Lead authors

Mariana F Fernandez (UGR)

Elena Salamanca (UGR)

Andrea Rodríguez-Carrillo (UGR)

Vicente Mustieles (UGR)

Nicolás Olea (UGR)

Contributors

Greet Schoeters (VITO), Kirsten Baken (VITO), Eva Govarts (VITO), Argelia Castaño (ISCIIII), Ludek Bláha (MU), Antonio Hernández (EASP), Marina Lacasaña (EASP), Tiina Saantonen (FIOH), Maria João Silva (INSA), Birgitte Lindeman (NIPH), Claudia Gundacker (MUW), Eva Cecilie Bonfeld-Jørgensen (AU), Anna-Maria Andersson (RegionH), Anne-Marie Vinggaard (DTU), Vicente Mustieles (UGR), Arthur David (INSERM), Shereen Cynthia (INSERM), Katrin Kreuzer (BfR), Jean-Baptiste Fini (CNRS), Jochem Louisse (RIKILT - RIVM), Tessa Schillemans (KI), Anteneh Desalegn (NIPH), Nina Iszatt (NIPH), Sylvie Remy (VITO), Andrea Rodríguez (UGR), Fabio Barbone (EPIUD), Valentina Rosolen (EPIUD), Gudrun Koppen (VITO)

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1 Abstract/Summary

Background: After 5 years of joint work, Work Package 14 (WP14) "Biomarkers of effect" wanted to pool and discuss the results of all activities undertaken by the integrated groups and to reflect on whether these had contributed to the research objectives included in Pillar 3 of the HBM4EU project. The activities entrusted to WP14 had been divided into two main lines (or tasks); that is, on the one hand by developing experimental studies and in human population (epidemiological study). Both aimed at validating or implementing (novel) biomarkers of effect. All this work was planned through the establishment of collaborations with other work packages, since without the involvement of the project as a whole the interesting advances in the understanding of the mode of action of environmental chemicals and their translation into policy (ultimate goal of HBM4EU) could not have been achieved.

Objective: To pool and discuss all activities (experimental, epidemiological) performed by WP14 partners and publications related to these activities, with special interest in the selection, validation and implementation of biomarkers of effect performed by WP14 partners (in collaboration with other partners and HBM4EU-WPs).

Results: Many interesting results (some still preliminary data) were showed regarding the implementation of novel effect biomarkers (kisspeptin and BDNF)) in the HBM4EU Aligned studies and in some established European cohorts (e.g. GENEIDA, INMA, PELAGIE) were summarised. Overall, experimental, and epidemiological studies showed for example that BDNF and kisspeptin could be used as novel effect biomarkers to detect birth health outcomes, misbalance in the hormonal pathway, and neurodevelopmental alterations due to some environmental chemicals exposure. Others promising novel effect biomarkers such as metabolomics or markers of lipid peroxidation seemed plausible markers within the purposes of HBM4EU.

Conclusions: The "3rd Granada Workshop" represented an important step forward for the consolidation of WP14 objectives, and the collaborative activities with other work-packages. All attending participants interacted to pursue specific goals to face the final stage of HBM4EU Project.

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2 List of abbreviations

AA:	Acrylamide
AA-Hb:	AA-Haemoglobin adducts
AOPs:	Adverse outcome pathways
AAMA:	N-Acetyl-S-(2-carbamoylethyl)-L-cysteine
BDNF:	Brain-derived neurotrophic factor
BP-1:	Benzophenone-1
BP-3:	Benzophenone-3
CBCL:	Child Behaviour Checklist
Cr(VI):	Hexavalent chromium
DAPs:	Dialkylphosphates
DE:	Diethylphosphate
DEHP:	Di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate
DINCH:	1,2-Cyclohexane dicarboxylic acid diisononyl ester
FSH:	Follicle stimulating hormone
FRs:	Flame retardants
GAMA:	N-Acetyl-S-(2-carbamoyl-2-hydroxyethyl)-L-cysteine
GFAP:	Glial fibrillary acidic protein
H3K4me3:	Histone H3K4 trimethylation
HRMS:	High-resolution mass spectrometry
IGF2:	Insulin like growth factor
KISS-1:	Kisspeptin-1
LOD:	Limit of detection
MBP:	Mono-n-butyl phthalate
MBzP:	Mono-benzyl phthalate
MEHP:	Mono (2-ethylhexyl) Phthalate
NAM:	National Accounting Matrix
NFH:	Neurofilament-heavy chain
NRGN:	Neurogranin
OP:	Organophosphate
OPCs:	Organophosphate compounds
OPFRs:	Organophosphate flame retardants
PBK/D:	Physiologic based kinetic/dynamic
PBPK:	Physiologically based pharmacokinetic

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PFAS:	Perfluoroalkylated substances
PFDA:	Perfluorodecanoic acid
PFHxS:	Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid
PFOS:	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
S100B:	Brain-specific S-100 protein
SHBG:	Sex Hormone Binding Globulin
THRA:	Thyroid hormone receptor alpha
THRB:	Thyroid hormone receptor beta
TT:	Testosterone
U-Cr:	Creatinine in urine
UCHL1:	Ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase L1
WP:	Work Package

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3 Overview of Work Package 14

Author: Marieta Fernandez (UGR)

The UGR, as WP14 leader, has hosted again the third "WP14 Granada Workshop" with the aim to present the main results obtained during the five years of work and to discuss important issues related to the end of the HBM4EU project. The present deliverable (AD14.7) aims to provide a summary of the workshop, presenting the state of development of all tasks and interactions carried out in WP14.

First of all, the WP14 leader (Marieta Fernández) welcomed the attendees and reviewed the progress made by the partners in all the tasks planned within the WP. Marieta Fernández, summarised how the scientific work of WP14 had been organised in four main areas:

1. Structured and comprehensive literature reviews to identify and prioritise the most relevant biomarkers of effect, related to the selected chemical families in the two prioritised sets. Following that approach, WP14 has been able to build an inventory of biomarkers of effect based on scientific knowledge, including adverse outcome pathways (AOPs), and Physiologic based kinetic/dynamic (PBK/D) modelling data in a biomarker of effect framework. Within the inventory, novel effect biomarkers (molecular and biochemical) that could support a causal link between exposure to environmental pollutants and adverse health effects were prioritised.
2. Validation of novel effect biomarkers at both analytical and physiological levels. This was carried out as proof of concept by conducting epidemiological pilot studies in existing European prospective cohorts.
3. Development of new biomarkers of combined effect to chemical mixtures that resemble human exposure in the real world.
4. Understanding of biological mechanisms behind effect biomarkers. This was performed through original experimental research using in vitro and/or in vivo models that may help to fill some knowledge gaps.

All these WP14 activities are helping (and will ultimately help), to achieve the main initial HBM4EU objective, to integrate biomarkers of effect alongside biomarkers of exposure in HBM studies, both general and occupational, and thus to better elucidate the relationships between exposure to mixtures of chemicals in the environment and health outcomes. This, in turn, will better inform regulatory risk assessments. The implementation of selected biomarkers of effect in the HBM4EU aligned studies is now our ultimate goal of WP14.

The WP leader reviewed how the effort has been translated into papers, with more than 25 scientific articles published in peer-reviewed journals, and a dozen more in the finalisation phase (30.5% of HBM4EU publications so far - 25 out of 82 publications, Figure 2), which is making a huge contribution to the project (see hbm4eu website <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/result/publications-2/>). Publications are a very important part of the outcome of the work developed by WP14 partners within this project. At the workshop, it was reminded the importance to keep up to date with publications from other project partners. Please join the Science Digest Newsletter mailing list where you can also read back issues.

Figure 2: WP14 publications inside HBM4EU (February 2022)

In this sense, it was highlighted that 37.5% of WP14 peer-reviewed papers have been published in very high impact journals (Figure 3, Decile 1) and 50% in the first quartile of their category. This reflects the very high quality of the work published and shows the scientific interest of the results being achieved.

Distribution of WP14 publications

Figure 3: WP14 distribution of publications

In addition, the publications planned for the end of the project were discussed and an overview was given of the forecast of titles, authors and groups involved.

Moreover, the fruitful collaborations of WP14 with other HBM4EU WPs (Figure 4) have yielded many results and scientific output over the years of the project and continue to yield results and collaborations for future studies. In this regard, WP14 has centralised the analysis of classical and novel biomarker.

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Figure 4: WP14 interaction with other WPs

Furthermore, it was discussed how WP14 outcomes can be used to answer the Policy Questions drawing the following conclusions on the use of WP14 research for Risk Assessment:

- Increase the weight of evidence and improve the evaluation of biological plausibility in HBM studies of the causal relationship between exposure and adverse health outcome
- Use of an AOP-based testing strategy to support chemical safety assessment within a NAM-based framework
- Different approaches for handling the complexity of effect biomarker utility
- Improvement in the assessment of complex real-world chemical mixtures

However, there is still much more to be done in effect biomarker discovery and validation to be applied in chemical safety assessment. Therefore, the next European partnership PARC will bring the opportunity to continue the work started in HBM4EU, strengthening the link between toxicology and HBM studies.

The agenda of the two working days was structured to allow an update on the activities included in the two WP14 tasks: **Task 14.1A**: Implementation and analysis of traditional and novel biomarkers of effect in HBM4EU-aligned studies and in existing European prospective cohorts, related to the first and second set of prioritised substances, and **Task 14.2A**: Experimental research to support biomarkers of effect in humans.

Interactions and collaborations established with other WPs of the project were also highlighted, and the participation of the leaders of these WPs was acknowledged.

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4 Implementation HBM4EU effect biomarkers (1st and 2nd set)

4.1 Implementation of novel effect biomarkers in the (1st/2nd) occupational studies

Authors: Maria João Silva, Tiina Santonen, (INSA&FIOH), and the HBM4EU chromates study team

In the frame of HBM4EU, a multi-national study was conducted across Europe to characterise occupational exposure to hexavalent chromium [Cr(VI)]. The use of Cr(VI) compounds (chromates and chromium trioxide) is authorised under the European regulation (EC 1907/2006) REACH and no alternative to the Cr(VI) use in some industrial activities has been found, so far. Workers exposure occurs mainly by inhalation while performing activities such as welding, Cr(VI) electroplating, and other surface treatment activities, but dermal contact may also be important.

This work aimed at characterising conventional and more promising effect biomarkers in blood and urine samples from groups of workers exposed to Cr(VI) and controls in order to explore the relationship between exposure, early biological effects and health outcomes.

All participants signed an informed consent and responded to a questionnaire to collect contextual information. Cr(VI) internal exposure was assessed by the measurement of total Cr in urine (U-Cr) from workers and control individuals. Workers were categorised according to the activities performed in bath platers, welders, chromate paint applicators, machining workers, and workers involved in other activities whereas controls were categorised in “within company controls” and “outwith company controls”, depending on whether they came from the same company where workers were recruited (e.g., office workers) or from companies not dealing with Cr(VI)- associated activities. The effect biomarkers characterised included conventional and novel biomarkers such as the alkaline comet assay, the cytokinesis-block micronucleus assay in peripheral blood leukocytes and reticulocytes, urinary oxidative stress markers (malondialdehyde, and 8-oxo-2'-deoxyguanosine), global methylation in DNA from leukocytes and metabolomics in urine.

Amongst workers from the industrial sectors studied the highest internal exposures (assessed by the U-Cr level) were related to the use of Cr(VI) in electrolytic bath plating. In contrast, welding activities were associated with the lowest internal exposure, which might be partly related to the lower bioavailability of Cr(VI) species formed during welding. The results of genotoxicity biomarkers in blood cells revealed that workers in electrolytic bath plating display the highest levels of DNA and chromosomal damage in leukocytes and the second highest level of chromosomal damage in reticulocytes. Welders exhibited the highest frequency of micronuclei in reticulocytes despite the lower U-Cr levels, suggesting recent exposure to Cr(VI) that might not have been captured by post-shift U-Cr levels. Given that in stainless steel welding exposure to nickel also occurs, this higher frequency of micronuclei in reticulocytes may also reflect a mixture effect. The frequency of micronucleated lymphocytes was significantly related to the U-Cr level with the highest exposed group (3rd tercile of U-Cr level) displaying the highest frequency of micronucleated cells. Likewise, the micronucleus frequency in reticulocytes was also related to the U-Cr level. The data of genotoxicity biomarkers also evidenced that controls recruited within the industries (e.g., office workers) displayed levels of genotoxic damage much higher than those of controls recruited outside the companies. Thus, although the selection of control groups constituted a limitation of the study, the finding reported above highlights the possibility of a bystander effect in office workers from companies where Cr(VI) is used. The comparison of global DNA methylation levels between the exposed and the control groups revealed a statistically significant decrease in levels observed in workers, suggesting deregulation of gene expression.

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The changes in abundance of urinary excreted metabolites observed in workers reflected fatty acid and monoamine neurotransmitter metabolism, oxidative modifications of the amino acid residues, excessive formation of abnormal amino acids metabolites and changes in steroid and thyrotropin-releasing hormone.

This work showed that, when biomarkers of effect supported by mechanistic knowledge are integrated together with biomarkers of exposure and the characterisation of the occupational setting, the early identification of occupational-related health effects is largely possible and the groups at highest risk for which mitigation measures should be prioritised.

The results of the implementation of biomarkers of effect in the remaining occupational studies carried out within the HBM4EU framework - **the HBM4EU E-waste and diisocyanates studies**- are currently being finalised.

4.2 Semi-targeted proteomic panel related with acrylamide exposure in Euromix

Author: Birgitte Lindeman (NIPH)

An exploratory study has been performed to search for potential new acrylamide (AA)-associated biomarkers of effect in human plasma.

The main objective was to explore the application of plasma proteomic profiling for the identification of novel candidate biomarkers of neurologic effects. In this work, we implemented the Olink neurological panel and the inflammation panel (www.Olink.com) in the EuroMix human biomonitoring study population (Husoy et al. 2019) as an exploratory study to ponder whether these biomarker screening panels are useful tools to define targeted set of protein biomarkers that can be used in epidemiological studies.

For this purpose, the Euromix human biomonitoring study was used. The study includes a total of 144 healthy adults. This biomonitoring study was established at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) and was part of the EU funded project EuroMix “European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures”. In the Euromix study, two types of AA exposure biomarkers were available: i) AA-Haemoglobin adducts (AA-Hb) and ii) urinary levels of the mercapturic acid metabolites AAMA and GAMA from a 24 h urine sample. The mean levels of the exposure markers were: AAMA 152.8 µg, GAMA 12.1 µg and AA-Hb 35.6 pmol/g Hb.

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Figure 5: Associations with AA-Hb adducts

Euromix HBM study identified a few potential biomarkers of effect associated with AA exposure. None of the associations were significant after correction for multiple testing but four proteins, JAM-B, CNTN5, CLEC10A and EPHB6, were significantly associated with AA-Hb-adducts following a Lasso procedure. The associations with the AA-Hg-adducts were more numerous compared to those for the urinary AA exposure biomarkers. AA-Hb-adducts accumulate over the lifespan of the erythrocyte and thus represent the AA exposure during a period of up to 120 days whereas AAMA and GAMA urinary metabolites represents short time exposures. These proteins are candidates for inclusion in larger cohort studies and also for further examination in *in vitro* models of neurotoxicity.

Screening for potential protein biomarkers of effect in human plasma can be a valuable addition to metabolomic and transcriptomic data for the strengthening of causality and mode of action analysis in epidemiological studies. Promising markers, or groups of markers, can subsequently be integrated into epidemiological and experimental studies linking exposures to health effects.

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4.3 Placenta biomarkers and birth outcomes

Author: Claudia Gundacker (MUW)

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and kisspeptin-1 (KISS-1) are expressed in the human placenta and regulate placental development and fetal growth with implications for fetal and pregnancy health. It is not known whether BDNF and KISS-1 levels in maternal serum correlate with those in the placenta and umbilical cord serum. A marker that early and reliably indicates changes in BDNF/KISS1 expression in the placenta and/or altered levels in fetal serum, however, is of great value.

Maternal serum, cord serum, and whole placenta tissue from 65 healthy term pregnancies (30 female, 35 male neonates) were collected between July 2019 and October 2021 in the General Hospital Vienna to be analysed for BDNF (proBDNF, mature BDNF) and KISS-1 serum levels by ELISA. BDNF and KISS-1 expression levels in whole placenta aliquots stabilised in RNAlater solution were analysed by qPCR. Mature BDNF and proBDNF, and KISS-1 were quantified using the "Mature BDNF/proBDNF Combo Rapid ELISA Kit" (Biosensis, BEK-2240) and "KISS-1 Metastasis Suppressor (KISS-1) ELISA Kit" (antibodies-online, ABIN6962789) according to the manufacturer's protocol, respectively.

BDNF levels are higher in maternal serum than in cord serum, whereas the opposite is the case for KISS1. Female and male offspring show no differences in cord serum levels for BDNF and KISS1. Maternal BDNF serum levels correlate well with placental and cord serum levels, which is the case also for KISS1 ($P < 0.05$) indicating that maternal serum levels reflect placental and cord serum levels to sufficient and promising extent. This pilot study provides evidence that maternal serum levels of BDNF and KISS1 are correlated with placental BDNF and KISS1 levels in healthy term pregnancies, and indicates that placental BDNF and KISS1 level could be good effect biomarker for healthy term pregnancies. The significance and predictive value of placental BDNF and KISS1 levels for developmental disorders need further research.

Figure 6: KiSS levels (pg/mL) of 65 mother-neonate-pairs

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4.4 Biomarkers of combined PFAS effect on human placentas

Author: Eva Bonefeld-Jørgensen, (AU)

The AU team have performed serum single PFASs compound level analyses as well as Serum PFAS mixture and Placenta PFAS mixture induced estrogenic activity.

Perfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) are a diverse group of human-made chemicals used in a wide range of consumer products, including food packaging, cosmetics, and impregnated products e.g. textiles. Exposure of humans to PFASs are mainly through food and drinking water. Both human and *in vitro* studies of single PFAS compounds indicate that they interfere with the estrogen system. However, the human exposure is a complex mixture of PFAS having the potential to interact additively (Kjeldsen et al. 2013). We have previously shown that the estrogenic transactivity of PFAS mixtures extracted from serum of 702 Danish pregnant women was associated with lower birth weight and length (Bjerregaard-Olesen et al. 2019).

In HBM4EU WP14, we have extracted real-life PFAS mixtures from 25 Spanish human placenta homogenates and determined their estrogenic activity using two cell culture assays. We dissolved the placenta homogenates (16 g) in hexane and passed it through a glass column with dried aluminium oxide. Then further extracted the eluate using solid phase extraction, high-performance liquid chromatography, and weak anion exchange as described in Bjerregaard-Olesen et al. 2015. Using the MVLN estrogen receptor (ER)-luciferase reporter-gene assay and the proliferation assay (E-Screen), we assessed the estrogenic activity of the placenta PFAS extracts.

In the ER-luciferase reporter-gene assay, 52 % (13 of the 25) PFAS placenta extracts elicited significant ER transactivity. The median fold induction was 1.14 (0.93-1.28). In the presence of 24pM 17 β -estradiol (E2), 68 % (17 of the 25) extracts significantly further enhanced the E2-induced ER transactivity. The median fold induction was 1.24 (0.88-1.44). In the E-screen assay, 62.5% (15 of 24) PFAS extracts elicited significant cell proliferative effect. The median fold induction was 1.88 (1.00-3.67). The ER transactivity (extracts alone or extracts+E2) and the E-screen estrogenic-proliferation (extracts alone) did not correlated significantly.

The ER transactivity of extracts did not correlate significantly with the single PFAS concentrations. The ER transactivity of extracts+E2 and the E-screen estrogenic-proliferation (extracts alone) generally correlated negatively with the single PFAS concentrations. The correlations were significant for PFHxS and PFOS, and the ER transactivity of extracts+E2 correlated with PFDA and the principal component with all single PFASs.

ER transactivity and E-Screen oestrogen proliferation were significantly higher in non-smokers than in smokers. ER transactivity (extracts alone or extracts + E2) was inversely associated with birth weight, length and head circumference, although not significantly. Thus, PFAS mixtures in the real life placenta elicit (anti)estrogenic activities and could have the potential to negatively affect birth outcomes, although the associations were not significant in this study, which could be due to the low number of samples (n=25). This approach therefore needs to be replicated with a larger number of samples (placentas) from diverse populations with differential exposure to these contaminants of interest in order to draw firmer conclusions.

Figure 7: Pearson correlation between single PFAS concentrations and the placenta PFAS mixture induced ER-estrogen & E-screen assays

4.5 Benzophenone-3: Systematic integrative review of the toxicological and epidemiological evidence with meta-analysis of HBM studies

Authors: Vicente Mustieles, Anna-Maria Andersson, Anne-Marie Vinggaard (UGR-RegionH-DTU)

In this talk, the authors summarised a systematic integrative review of BP-3, including a meta-analysis of human biomonitoring data (submitted). An inventory of the evidence available was created. A human biomonitoring database was generated on BP-3 and BP-1. Around 250 references were tabulated and analysed, and their information was presented and discussed in an integrative way.

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Figure 8: Depicting the temporal and geographic worldwide distribution of BP-3 concentrations (log-scale).

The most relevant exposure sources and predictors were identified from the literature. The meta-analysis of HBM studies showed that urinary BP-3 concentrations were around 10- and 20- fold higher in North America compared to Europe and Asia, respectively. Although median urinary BP-3 concentrations usually found in Europe correspond to a low-dose range, top percentiles of population exposure (P90 and P95) are significantly higher, being possibly linked to peak-exposure scenarios after sunscreen and cosmetic use. Indeed, the review of human toxicokinetic studies highlighted that high internal free BP-3 concentrations are achieved in few hours after a unique whole-body exposure to a sunscreen formulation containing BP-3 at lower concentrations than those allowed by the current European regulation (max. 6% weight/weight of sunscreen formulation). Rat-to-human ratios were estimated comparing internal plasma BP-3 concentrations in adult rodents and humans.

More than 50 *in vitro* studies were tabulated, identifying the effects elicited at the lowest doses. More than 20 *in vivo* studies were tabulated and the most sensitive endpoints were highlighted and discussed. More than 60 human exposure-health studies were tabulated, discussing the ones that show a higher level of consistency. It was concluded that peak free BP-3 concentrations reached after whole-body dermal applications of sunscreen may overlap with levels causing *in vitro* and *in vivo* endocrine disrupting effects. Results also highlight that benzophenone-1 (BP-1), the major BP-3 metabolite, is considerably more estrogenic and anti-androgenic than BP-3, and shows a longer half-life.

While human toxicokinetic intervention studies only measured BP-3, human internal BP-1 data after sunscreen and cosmetic use is currently unknown, being this information important to improve the comparability between rodent and human toxicokinetic data. There is a need to assess BP-1 and BP-3 concentrations in cosmetic products commercialised in Europe, as well as to better characterise human peak-exposure scenarios after sunscreen and cosmetic use.

4.6 Effect Biomarkers in placenta from the PELAGIE cohort

Authors: Arthur David, Shereen D'Cruz, (INSERM)

Organophosphate (OP) pesticides are widely used in agriculture and the negative impacts of OP, and their metabolites on human health has been demonstrated. We hypothesised that exposure to OPs during pregnancy, specifically to diethylphosphate (DE) metabolites, could elicit damaging effects on the fetus by affecting various processes.

INSERM has presented the assessment of novel epigenetic effect biomarkers in placenta samples from the mother-child PELAGIE cohort (94 samples) and found there are sex-specific differences in repetitive elements in human placenta. The study assayed the telomere length and mitochondria copy numbers using genomic DNA in the placenta samples, performed analysis of histone epigenetic marks H3K4me3 by using chromatin immunoprecipitation followed by qPCR (ChIP-qPCR) and high throughput sequencing (ChIP-seq).

Figure 9: Circus plot showing alterations in H3k4me3

Results revealed a higher susceptibility of male-baby placentas to DE exposure. Specifically, a tendency for telomere length shortening, and an increase in the levels of gH2AX, a DNA damage marker, in male placentas were observed. We detected lower histone H3K9me3 occupancies at the telomere of DE-exposed male placenta compared to non-exposed. An increase in H3K4me3 occupancy at the promoters of thyroid hormone receptors alpha and beta (THRA, THRB) and 8-Oxoguanine DNA Glycosylase (OGG1) in female placentas was found. In contrast in male placentas, the increase at BDNF1 promoter was identified. H3K4me3 promoter occupancy at Insulin like growth factor (IGF2) was increased in both male and female placentas. Using ChIP-seq genome-wide sequencing of selected samples, sex-specific differences in unexposed samples (below the limit of quantification, LOQ) were observed. An increase in H3K4me3 in the genes related to immune system in female placenta samples compared to males was also found. In males, a decrease in H3K4me3 occupancy mainly at the promoters of cell fate commitment, collagen catabolic process and angiogenesis-related genes were noted when comparing with females' placental samples. The human study was confirmed with mouse placenta samples. Mice

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placenta samples showed a similar sexual dimorphism in the expression of some developmental genes and a higher level of H3K4me3 in males samples compared to females.

These data suggest that exposure to DE induces the sex-specific differences in epigenetics response at important developmental genes.

Metabolomics was carried out in the placenta for the identification of effect biomarkers. In this regard, INSERM performed a characterisation of the human internal chemical exposome using placenta and HRMS-based methods.

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5 Experimental research to support human effect biomarkers

5.1 Transcriptomic responses of human HepaRG and lymphoid TK6 cells after exposure to selected genotoxic and non-genotoxic substances- in search for potential effect biomarkers applicable to HBM studies.

Author: Katrin Kreuzer (BfR)

Most genotoxins act directly, or indirectly after metabolic activation, as electrophilic molecules that interact with DNA and induce respective damage. Depending of the level of cell injury, different cellular responses may occur. We addressed the question whether DNA damage is reflected in the transcriptome, and if transcripts can be considered as biomarkers for genotoxicity. Such biomarkers could contribute to risk assessment, by conceivably measuring the level of exposure or by classifying substances into genotoxic and non-genotoxic.

In order to answer this question, we performed literature research and *in vitro* analyses, especially RNA sequencing in two cell models, the metabolically competent human liver cell line HepaRG and human lymphoblastoid TK6 cells, as representatives of a genotoxin target tissue (liver) and blood as a matrix that can be easily obtained for analysis.

Following Ates et al., (2018) approach, BfR group performed RNA sequencing in the liver cell model HepaRG with five food-relevant genotoxins. From differentially expressed genes ($p_{adj} < 0.05$ and fold change > 1.5) the commonality was investigated. A number of 37 genes were regulated equally by all five substances and underwent further analysis to obtain a transcript signature as a potential biomarker for genotoxicity. Analyses with non-genotoxins demonstrated the specificity of the transcript marker pattern for genotoxicity.

Subsequent RNA sequencing using the lymphoblastoid TK6 cell line was performed as similar as possible to the HepaRG approach, including using the same compounds at the same concentrations, wherever possible. However, since TK6 cells hardly express any xenobiotic-metabolising enzymes, it was necessary to work with an S9 external metabolic activating system. Examining the overlap of the differentially expressed genes of the genotoxins revealed 116 genes regulated in common. Using partial least squares discriminant analysis, we were able to filter out marker candidate genes for a transcriptomic signature in TK6 cells.

Comparing the two RNA sequencing approaches showed clear differences between HepaRG and TK6 cells in the regulation of genotoxicity-responsive genes. In TK6 cells, hardly any of the HepaRG marker genes were affected by genotoxic treatment, and many genes were only regulated weakly.

In summary, we have shown in our laboratory work that transcriptomics can be used to derive *in vitro* gene signatures for genotoxicity. We worked with two cell systems, HepaRG and TK6 cells, and were able to identify a gene signature for genotoxicity in both cell lines individually. However, the HepaRG signature cannot be readily transferred one-to-one to the TK6 cells, indicating the difficulty of comparability of different cell lines. Transcript marker patterns may constitute a promising approach for biomarker development and possibly, blood samples may be used as a source of material for analyses indicative of damage in other tissues not easily accessible for biomarker studies.

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5.2 Experimental work done by CNRS to validate the effect biomarkers

Author: Jean-Baptiste Fini, (CNRS)

In this presentation, the CNRS showed how research on biomarkers of effect had been carried out within WP14 and how it had been articulated with other partners in HBM4EU WP13 and WP16.

The strategy was carried out in four phases: 1) use the inventory of prioritised substances performed by HBM4EU, 2) identify the knowledge gaps, 3) develop and validate effect biomarkers and biomarkers of combined effect (biomarkers to quantify the effect of real-world mixtures of chemical substances), and 4) contribute to the understanding of the links between exposure and health.

The research began with a literature search on bisphenols. The example of the work was carried out with partners from the University of Granada (Spain), IRSET (Rennes, France), INSERM (Paris, France) and the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (Norway). The search for biomarkers of effects and their experimental validation started with the support of the inventory of prioritised chemicals developed in HBM4EU and the identification of gaps in knowledge (neurodevelopment, epigenetic markers on neurodevelopment, reproduction...). Specific search equations could be described to list biomarkers of known or less known effects on health domains such as neurodevelopment, reproduction, metabolism, or cancer. A total of 5581 articles were processed. Qualitative and quantitative criteria were used to identify new biomarkers of potential interest. We were able to identify proteins such as BDNF, GDNF, SP4, or kisspeptin as potential biomarkers for neurodevelopmental and reproductive disorders.

In identifying knowledge gaps, the CNRS has worked on the link between effect biomarkers and AOPs by doing several experimental studies. Thus, the CNRS has worked on a review and fine-tuning of 3R models (*in vitro* replacement, reduction and refinement) compliant with thyroid assessment (Couderq et al, 2020), since thyroid function plays a key role in the whole process of neurodevelopment. In addition, this working model has been extended to other priority substances, such as pesticides and mercury, leading to the identification of new molecular targets involved, such as membrane hormone transporters. As a result of this work, two reviews have been published (Leemans et al, 2019; Andersen et al submitted). Finally, a collaborative work on the identification of new epigenetic biomarkers following mercury exposure has led to the detection of promising biomarkers of effect, e.g. hypomethylation of PON1 in newborns or hypomethylation of pSEPP1 in adults (Couderq et al review submitted).

Several experimental works have been carried out in order to validate the biomarkers identified by the literature review work,

- 1) On biomarkers of combined effect, a collaborative work involving partners from WP14 and WP16 has allowed to test the endocrine effects of real-world chemical mixtures previously extracted from placental samples (Rodríguez-Carrillo et al., 2021).
- 2) CNRS also tested the impact of exposure to bisphenols and mercury on the expression of genes including the BDNF gene using a 3R-compliant model. CNRS also created a model of hypothyroidism by crispr cas9: the MCT 8 KO model (mutant for the MCT8 membrane transporter and model for human Allan Herndon Dudley syndrome). This model suggests that the transcriptomal changes observed with xenobiotics occur via a thyroid disruption mode of action (Couderq et al, in preparation).

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In conclusion, the experimental validation that had been conducted for the biomarkers is both useful and necessary for future global use of these biomarkers and to identify the mechanisms (here thyroid hormone). Thus, the experimentation has confirmed the correlation established from the epidemiological data, but there is also a need to conduct translational studies and to construct reliable AOPs.

5.3 Experimental research on PFAS mechanisms and lipid metabolism

Author: Jochem Louisse, (RIKILT - RIVM)

During the workshop, the results of the *in vitro* studies performed by WFSR (former RIKILT) and RIVM were presented. The studies performed aimed to get more insight into the molecular effects of poly- and perfluoralkyl substances (PFASs) in the human liver by studying effects on gene expression and triglyceride accumulation in the human HepaRG liver cell line.

These data can be used to assess whether the effects reported in humans relating internal PFAS levels to changes in plasma cholesterol and lipids, can be supported by mechanistic data. Also, data were obtained to get more insight into (*in vitro*) potency differences of in total 18 PFASs. Furthermore, at the applied exposure conditions, cellular PFAS levels were obtained for PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS and PFOS and these data were used for quantitative *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation (QIVIVE) of the *in vitro* toxicity data of these 4 PFASs (Fragki et al., 2021; Louisse et al., 2020)

Transcriptomic data of PFOS-exposed HepaRG cells show that various cellular processes are affected in a concentration-dependent manner, including processes related to cholesterol and lipid biosynthesis. The obtained data do not directly support the observed *in vivo* effects in human studies, but cannot exclude these either. Ten genes were selected showing clear concentration-dependent changes and the effects of 18 PFASs on the expression of these genes in HepaRG cells was determined using qPCR analyses. These data were used to obtain *in vitro* relative potency factors (RPFs) for all PFASs, setting the potency of PFOA at 1 (index chemical).

These RPFs were compared with RPFs related to PFAS-induced liver toxicity in rats, as reported in the literature. For some genes a good *in vitro-in vivo* correlation was obtained, indicating that the *in vitro* model is expected to provide relevant insights into relative potencies of PFASs regarding liver toxicity.

6 PFASs showed concentration-dependent increase Response at max 1.4-fold (limited effect window)

Parallel curve fitting

Figure 10: AdipoRed assay (triglyceride increase)

Biokinetic studies show that cellular PFAS accumulation differs between PFASs. The data were used for the QIVIVE of *in vitro* toxicity data to oral equivalent dose levels. Since there is no generally accepted best approach regarding the dose metric used for QIVIVE, different approaches were evaluated (1: liver concentration *in vivo* = nominal concentration *in vitro*; 2: liver concentration *in vivo* = nominal concentration *in vitro* x partition coefficient liver; and 3: liver concentration *in vivo* = cellular concentration *in vitro*, scaled to the liver), showing differences in oral equivalent dose levels. It was shown that the choice of dose metric will affect relative potencies estimated based on oral equivalent doses obtained by QIVIVE. Oral equivalent dose levels will be compared with data on exposure and health based guidance values.

5.4 Synergies with WP13: updates and relevant activities

Author: Ludek Blaha, (MU)

In HBM4EU WP13 we integrate mechanistic toxicology (Adverse Outcome Pathways, AOPs) with cohort studies to understand relationships between human exposures to priority compounds and health. Effect biomarkers are of high relevance to WP13 as their identification and validation (biological plausibility) are directly linked to AOPs, and cohorts (validation in along with health effects in human studies). In this presentation, overview of activities and research outcomes from WP13 that are specifically relevant to Effect Biomarker is provided along with discussions of the most important synergies with HBM4EU WP14. The examples given include association studies on PFAS, acrylamide, PAHs and metals with diverse health outcomes in cohort studies (D13.7- Final report on exposure-response associations based on pre-existing cohort data for the 1st and 2nd list of priority substances).

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Further, we highlight case research studies linking HBM, PBPK, in vitro and cohorts (WP13 internal call projects on PFAS and mixture toxicity) or AOP-based studies that supported biological plausibility in endocrine toxicities of phthalates, flame retardants or bisphenols.

Further, new review was prepared on pyrethroids using epidemiological studies and mechanistic evidence that collected evidences on developmental neurotoxicity of this class of priority compounds. The presentation also highlights connecting nodes in AOPs of multiple compounds that strongly indicate importance of some mechanisms (lipid metabolic disruption) for multiple classes of chemicals such as PFAS and flame retardants.

These evidences indicates that common shared mechanisms may greatly contribute to mixture toxicities. The presentation also shows how AOPs and effect biomarkers can serve to prioritisation (and potentially to risk assessment) of data-poor chemicals such as novel organic flame retardants or novel bisphenols. The presented examples include endocrine disruptive potential (via modulation of multiple nuclear receptors) as well as implementation of novel bioinformatics tools such as AOP-help finder.

Finally, new evidence is presented on mycotoxin fumonisin B1, where toxicological information combined with AOPs (in vitro) and data from human studies allowed to identify novel biomarker - increase of sphinganine/sphingosine ratio (Sa/So) in urine is associated with fumonisin (FB1) exposures, and can be linked also to the health outcome - neural tube defects. In summary, cooperation and synergies between WP13 and WP14 during HBM4EU delivered a range of advancements in linking human exposures and health that can be explained (and predicted) through analyses of effect biomarkers.

5.5 GENEIDA study assessing molecular biomarkers of brain damage

Author: Antonio Hernández (EASP)

Organophosphate compounds (OPCs), covering both pesticides and flame retardants, are systemic toxicants affecting virtually every organ system, though they primarily affect the central nervous system, particularly the developing brain as these compounds demonstrated to be neurodevelopmental toxicants in animals. A direct link exists between low-level OPCs exposure during early development and deficits in neurobehavioral-cognitive performance evident late in childhood.

EASP partner has assessed the association between prenatal exposure to OPCs (organophosphate flame retardants –OPFRs– and dialkylphosphates –DAPs– metabolites of organophosphate pesticides) on biomarkers of brain damage and neurodevelopmental outcomes at 1 and 2 years of age in the population participating in the GENEIDA birth cohort (Genetics, Early Life Environmental Exposures and Infant Development in Andalucía), an existing European cohort.

The study population involved 800 pregnant women and their children. A set of biological samples properly collected and stored at -80°C were collected:

- Mother during pregnancy: Serum, plasma, whole blood, urine, nails, hair and stool
- Delivery: Placenta (stored within RNAlater TissueProtect Tubes and standard tubes), cord blood (serum, plasma, whole blood, whole blood-RNAlater).
- Children (1, 2 and 4 year-old): urine, feces, nails, hair.

Urine samples were collected at first (1T, n=528) and third (3T, n=502) trimesters of pregnancy and analysed for OPCs using LC-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS. Urinary samples were analysed (7 OPFRs and 3 DAPs) as well as the molecular biomarkers of neurotoxicity and neurodevelopmental

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domains. As biomarkers of potential neurotoxicity we studied brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), neurogranin (NRGN), ubiquitin C-terminal hydrolase L1 (UCHL1), neurofilament-heavy chain (NFH), glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) and brain-specific S-100 protein (S100B) in cord blood (n=465). Multiplex analysis based on the Luminex xMAP technology was performed using a customised commercial kit (Invitrogen ProcartaPlex Preconfigured Neurobiology Panel, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Neurodevelopmental outcomes were evaluated using cognitive, motor, and language domains of the Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (Bayley-III) at 1-2 years of age. OCPs levels below the detection limit (LOD) were imputed by assigning a random value between 0 and the LOD. Multiple linear regression models were adjusted for creatinine levels and potential confounders to evaluate the association between OPCs metabolite levels for each time window of exposure (T1 and T3) and the biomarkers of neurotoxicity studied (log-transformed) and scores for the neurodevelopmental domains of Bayley-III as dependent variables. As levels of UCHL1 and NFH were below the LOD in more than half of the blood cord samples analysed, a dichotomous variable was built (levels above or below LOD) and adjusted multiple logistic regression analysis was used instead.

Significant associations between levels of OPCs and molecular biomarkers of brain damage at 1T and 3T, particularly with decreased BDNF and NRGN, and increased UCLH1 levels were found. In regards to neurodevelopmental domains, OPFRs showed a positive association with motor domain (fine and composite) at 2 years whereas DAPs were inversely associated with motor score and language (receptive) at 1 and 2 years of age. Significant inverse associations between biomarkers of brain damage (NRGN) and the three neurodevelopmental domains at 1 year of age, i.e. cognition (total score and composite) language (receptive, expressive, composite) and motor (gross, composite), were also observed.

At 2 years of age, NRGN was found to be inversely associated with motor domain (fine, gross and composite), GFAP inversely associated with motor (gross and composite), UCLH1 positively associated with motor (fine and composite), and BDNF positively associated with cognition (total score and composite). The association of BDNF with language (expressive and composite) depended on the sex, as a positive association, was found in girls whereas boys showed an inversely association.

Overall, and despite some limitations, this proof of concept study provided novel insight into a selection of candidate biomarkers of neurotoxicity measured in cord blood of healthy neonates which have promise for identification of potential neurotoxicity related to prenatal exposure to OPCs. We also observed a comprehensive correlation between the molecular biomarkers studied and the neurodevelopmental domains assessed by the Bayley-III, suggesting a common toxicological pathway.

Prenatal exposure to OPFRs and neurodevelopment at 1 year of age

1st Trimester

		Bayley III subscale (1 year)	ALL			BOYS			GIRLS					
			Beta	95% CI		p-value	Beta	95% CI		p-value	Beta	95% CI		p-value
				Low	High			Low	High			Low	High	
OPFRs metabolites (1 st TRIMESTER)	Log DPP	Cognitive (subscale)				0,526	-0,015	1,066	0,057					
		Cognitive (composite)				2,628	-0,075	5,331	0,057					
		Language (expressive)								0,296	-0,051	0,643	0,095	
		Language (receptive)												
	Language (composite)													
	Motor (fine)					0,508	-0,093	1,109	0,097					
	Motor (gross)													
	Motor (composite)													
Log Σ OPFRs	Cognitive (subscale)													
	Cognitive (composite)													
	Language (expressive)													
	Language (receptive)													
	Language (composite)									-0,961	-1,914	-0,008	0,048	
	Motor (fine)													
	Motor (gross)													
Motor (composite)														

Figure 11: Prenatal exposure to OPFRs and neurodevelopment at 1 year of age

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6 WP10 exposure-effect analysis and pathways

6.1 PFASs and Metabolism/BMI in teenagers

Author: Tessa Schillemans (KI)

In this presentation, KI showed its investigation on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, which are widespread pollutants that may impact youth adiposity patterns, and can increase disease risk later in life. Improved knowledge on preventable risk factors is therefore imperative for population health. Their aim was to investigate cross-sectional associations between per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances and BMI in teenagers across nine different countries in Europe using data from the Horizon 2020 project on human biomonitoring in Europe 'HBM4EU'.

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances were measured in blood in 1957 participants from different cohorts in Europe (NEBII, Norway; Riksmaten Ungdom 2016-17, Sweden; PCB cohort follow-up, Slovakia; SLO CRP, Slovenia; CROME, Greece; BEA, Spain; ESTEBAN, France; FLEHS IV, Belgium; GerES V-sub, Germany). Baseline cross-sectional associations between ten different PFAS levels and age- and sex-adjusted BMI were assessed using linear regression analysis adjusted for age, sex, household education status and fish consumption. Additionally, multivariable-adjusted logistic regression was used to investigate associations between PFAS and odds of overweight. Random-effects meta-analysis and mixed effects models were used to pool cohorts. Further adjustment for breastfeeding and birthweight as well as stratification by sex were explored in sensitivity analyses.

They observed low levels of PFAS concentrations and found inverse associations of PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA and PFUnDA with age- and sex-adjusted BMI (β -coefficient (95% CI) per 1-interquartile range increase in log transformed PFAS = -0.22 (-0.34, -0.11), -0.08 (-0.14, -0.02), -0.07 (-0.13, -0.01), -0.12 (-0.21, -0.04) and -0.11 (-0.22, -0.01), respectively). The results were not impacted by adjustment for breastfeeding or birthweight, but inverse associations were stronger for males. Their results indicated a tendency for inverse associations between PFAS levels and BMI in European adolescents. More prospective research is needed to investigate this potential inverse relationship and its implications for health later in life. Once all the statistical analyses have been carried out, the manuscript will be drafted including the discussion of the literature on PFAS and anthropometric measures.

6.2 Phthalates/DINCH & FRs and Metabolism/BMI in children/teenagers

Author: Anteneh Desalegn, Nina Iszatt (NIPH)

Childhood overweight and obesity are strong predictors of various cardiovascular diseases later in life. Exposure to ever-increasing number of chemicals from the environment during critical periods of development may explain the obesity epidemic.

The aim of this study, led by NIPH, was to evaluate the association between phthalates (DINCH) and flame retardants (FRs) exposure and the risk of overweight/obesity among European children and teenagers using HBM4EU collaborative multi-centre study.

We performed a cross-sectional study using data from 12 countries (InAirQ, Hungary; NACII-IT, Italy; GerESV, German; NEBII, Norway; ESTEBAN, France; POLAES, Poland; PCB cohort, Slovakia; SLOCRP, Slovenia; CROME, Greece; OCC, Denmark; Specimen, Netherland; 3xG, Belgium) for children, and 10 countries (GerESV, German; NEBII, Norway, ESTEBAN, France; POLAES, Poland; PCB-follow-up, Slovakia; SLOCRP, Slovenia; CROME, Italy; Riksmaten, Sweden; BEA-ES, Spain; FLEHSIV, Belgium) for teenagers across Europe.

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Mixed effect models were used to assess the association between urine levels of 14 phthalates (DINCH) and 6 flame retardants with BMI z-score (linear mixed model) and overweight/obesity (mixed effect logistic regression) adjusting for age, sex, and household education status. Further individual adjustment for birthweight, breastfeeding, maternal smoking, and consumption of food from plastic packaging were used as a sensitivity analysis. Potential effect modification by sex was also assessed. Missing values for covariates and exposure values were also imputed.

In general, we didn't observe evidence of association between exposure to phthalates with both BMI z-score and overweight. Exposure misclassification due to the short half-life of phthalates and its metabolites can't be ruled out.

Outcome (Obesity/bmi z score)

Figure 12: Obesity/BMI Z score

6.3 Phthalates/DINCH & PFASs and Sexual Maturation in teenagers

Author: Sylvie Remy (VITO)

Sylvie Remy, on behalf of the VITO working group showed the preliminary results of the on-going analyses of phthalate and PFAS exposure and sexual maturation in seven HBM4EU aligned studies. A total of 10 phthalates (15 metabolites), as well as DINCH (2 metabolites) and 12 PFASs have been measured. The study population included a total of 1741 European adolescents. The first statistical models have analysed by multiple regression the relationship between age at menarche and tanning scores.

So far, multiple regression has been completed for studies that have both age at menarche and tanning scores. The analysis was adjusted for age and socioeconomic status (SES), and creatinine for phthalates. In addition, influential outliers were removed and smokers were excluded.

Preliminary results obtained only with the FLEHSIV cohort data indicate that PFAS exposure increases the risk of delayed genital development, mainly among boys, although the results found were not statistically significant. No relationship was found between PFAS exposure and breast development (telarche); however PFAS exposure was related with delayed age of menarche,

especially with exposure to some compounds: PFAS, MBZP and OH-MIDP (when all data from HBM4EU aligned studies were included). Exposure to MBZP, OH-MEHP and MEHP was also found to be associated with earlier age at menarche.

All these results will be finalised and ready for publication before the end of the HBM4EU European project.

Results: tanner scores

BE – VITO FLEHSIV

Females: Breast development

Males: Genital development

PFAS
DINCH
PHTHALATES

- ✓ Adjusted for age and SES (ISCED HH) (and crt for phthalates)
- ✓ Influential outliers removed
- ✓ Smokers excluded

Figure 13: Tanner scores genital development

Results: Age menarche

DE - UBA GerES V

- ✓ Adjusted for age and SES (ISCED HH) (and crt for phthalates)
- ✓ Influential outliers removed
- ✓ Smokers excluded

Figure 14: Age at menarche

6.4 Phthalates/DINCH & PFASs, hormonal profile & kisspeptin in the FLEHS cohort

Author: Andrea Rodríguez (UGR)

The on-going analysis on cross-sectional associations between phthalates, PFAS and steroid, pituitary hormones, and serum kisspeptin (kisspeptin 54) were presented. FLESH cohort was first selected for preliminary analyses, due to data availability. Exposure biomarkers were log-transformed, and phthalates additionally standardised by creatinine levels. Classical and novel effect biomarkers were log-transformed as well. Due to the sex-dependent nature of reproductive hormones, analyses were divided according to sex (n=103 boys and n= 136 girls). Deliverable 10.10, literature evidence, and correlation analyses were consulted to select the appropriate covariates for adjustment of the models.

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Thus, two models were performed:

- Model 1: age (+creatinine for phthalates)
- Model 2: age, waist to height ratio, and household education (+creatinine for phthalates)

Firstly, heatmap correlation analyses (Figure 15) were performed to ascertain the degree of correlation among PFAS (5 metabolites: PFOA, PFNA, PFHXS, PFOS, and PFDA) and phthalates (14 metabolites: mbzp, mibp, mnbp, mehps, ohmehp, oxomehp, cxmepp, mep, mhnp, mcp, ohmidp, cxmidp, mhnc, and mcoch).

Figure 15: Heatmaps addressing the correlation among PFAS metabolites (PFOA, PFNA, PFHXS, PFOS, and PFDA) and phthalates metabolites (mbzp, mibp, mnbp, mehps, ohmehp, oxomehp, cxmepp, mep, mhnp, mcp, ohmidp, cxmidp, mhnc, and mcoch).

Afterwards, multivariate linear regression models were used to ascertain the relationship between PFAS/Phthalates metabolites and kisspeptin and reproductive hormones. Main results indicated that sex-dependent associations are found when assessing exposure and effect biomarkers. There were also different patterns of association according to the chemical family evaluated (e.g. PFAS vs Phthalates), as shown in Figure 16:

- PFAS showed associations with higher serum kisspeptin and lower testosterone concentrations in adolescent males. Conversely, associations with higher follicle stimulating, estradiol hormones concentrations and lower sex hormone binding globulin concentrations were found in adolescent **females**.
- Phthalates showed consistent negative associations with follicle stimulating hormone and total testosterone concentrations in adolescent **males**. Not consistent associations were found for adolescent females.

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Figure 16: Main cross-sectional associations found between PFAS/Phthalates and kisspeptin and hormonal concentrations in adolescents from FLESH cohort (male= 103, female=136).

Future steps should be considered to continue with analyses development, such as:

- Include data from the rest of cohorts (BEA, PCB, SLO CRP, and NEB II).
- Consider the sum of relevant PFAS and phthalates metabolites
- Explore the associations between kisspeptin and hormone levels.
- Include the information provided by the methylation of KISS1 gene.

6.5 Phthalates/DINCH & FRs and Neurodevelopment in children

Author: UGR – Vicente Mustieles / EPIUD – Fabio, Valentina

This presentation showed the preliminary associations between urinary phthalate metabolites and non-persistent flame retardant concentrations with behavioural function among children from the NAC (Italy) cohort.

First, exposure biomarkers were standardised by urinary dilution (adjustment in models were also considered), and log-transformed. To analyse Child Behaviour Checklist (CBCL), both linear regression and negative binomial regression models were considered. BDNF biomarkers were analysed following linear regression being possibly log-transformed depending on their distributions. Moreover, sex-specific associations were considered based on the literature and covariates were selected based on causal knowledge (DAG). Sensitivity analyses were applied to test further adjustment for relevant covariates not included in main model but that may be relevant outcome or exposure predictors without being a consequence of the exposure.

For CBCL, the preliminary analysis showed some positive associations between mono-n-butyl phthalate (MBP) and di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (DEHP) metabolites in relation to externalising problems among boys (see Figure 17 below). Notwithstanding, the authors expect to include at least one additional HBM4EU aligned study cohort apart from NAC, to achieve a better geographical representation and statistical power. One conclusion is that there is scarcity of behavioural and BDNF data available in the aligned studies.

Although the aligned studies will provide interesting original data on BDNF and neurodevelopment, to really close data gaps there is a need to evaluate these associations in new European mother-child cohorts, including the so-called «third-generation cohorts», with longitudinal repeated measurements of both exposures, effect biomarkers and outcomes: i) multiple repeated urine samples to limit exposure misclassification; ii) multiple BDNF measurements at several points in early childhood to assess temporal variability; and iii) repeated neuropsychological outcomes to

study neurodevelopmental trajectories throughout childhood. Indeed, the implementation of repeated BDNF measurements in third-generation cohorts appears as a natural continuation of the promising work initiated in HBM4EU, that can be performed in subsequent European projects such as for example the forthcoming PARC initiative.

Externalizing CBCL scores

Figure 17: Preliminary cross-sectional associations with CBCL data in the NAC cohort at 6-7 years of age (N=299)

The second part of the presentation was about the preliminary results of the association between Phthalates/DINCH exposure and child neurodevelopment WISC. This study tried to estimate the association between the child’s neurological development and the exposure to phthalates/DINCH in the three children cohorts (PCB, NAC II, OCC). The neurodevelopment of children was assessed using the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children (WISC) test. The WISC provides a measure of general intellectual ability of the children that is the Full Scale IQ (FSIQ) score.

The preliminary results showed that in the NAC II cohort there were positive associations between the Full scale IQ and some phthalates/DINCH exposures. Thus, compared to the Human biomonitoring guidance values the concentration levels in the NAC II cohort are very low.

Figure 18: Main model: Child age at CBCL assessment, child sex, child BMI, and maternal/paternal education. Ethnicity not included due to low variability.

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6.6 Phthalates/DINCH (children) and PFASs (teenagers) and Asthma and allergy

Author: Gudrun Koppen, (VITO)

In molecular epidemiological studies, exposure to per- and polyfluorinated (PFAS) compounds used in several coatings, as well as plasticisers such as phthalates and DINCH is shown to be relatively weak and sometimes inconsistent associated with asthma and allergic disorders.

The study carried out by VITO team, aimed performing meta-analyses of aligned studies of HBM4EU in children and teenagers to explore the link between PFAS and plasticisers vs allergic disorders.

Five European children cohorts in the age range of 6-12 years old (average 8.2y, N=1144, NACII (IT), SLOCRP (SK), InAirQ (HU), GerES-V (DE), 3xG (BE)) and four teenager cohorts in the age range of 12-18y old (average 14.2y, N=678, SLOCRP (SL), POLAES (PL), GerES-V (DE), FLEHS-4 (BE)) were included in the study. Ten phthalates+DINCH compounds were measured in urine of children. In teenagers, both, these plasticisers and 12 PFAS were measured in urine and serum respectively. Allergic disorder outcomes were collected via self-reported questionnaires, namely: eczema, rhinitis, food allergy, other allergies and asthma. Multivariate logistic regression was performed per country. In case too little health outcome cases were available in the country cohort, the statistical analysis was not performed for that cohort. The Odds Ratio for an increase in exposure change of P_{75}/P_{25} was assessed. Adjustment of the models was done for sex, age, passive smoking and highest education of the family.

The prevalence of the allergic disorders could not always be compared as such, due to differences in the questions used among the countries (e.g. either questioned as 'ever occurring' or 'doctor diagnosed' or asked via an open question). Overall, the asthma prevalence was very low in the children's cohorts (<4%) and therefore this outcome was not used in the statistical analysis. The asthma prevalence was, as expected higher in the teenager cohorts (8-9%).

Asthma - teenagers

NB: children: too little asthma cases

Figure 19: Asthma- DICH, phthalates and PFAS in teenagers

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However, no associations were observed between exposures and asthma in teenagers. In children, eczema was non-significantly positively associated with secondary metabolites of the phthalate DEHP and a primary metabolite of DnBP in 3 of 4 cohorts. This was not seen in teenagers. Rhinitis in children was non-significantly positively associated with DINCH exposure in 2 out of 3 of the cohorts. In teenagers, PFOA showed to be positively, non-significantly associated with rhinitis in both cohorts having these data.

As allergic disorder prevalence changes with age, it was interesting to evaluate the associations in both age groups. The associations that were consistently seen in at least two of the populations of the age group, were weak and often not significant. Nonetheless, it still may have a substantial impact, as the European children and teenager population is widely exposed to those chemicals.

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7 Conclusions

WP14's initial HBM4EU proposal to select, validate and implement some novel and traditional biomarkers of clinical effect, both in existing European studies, as proof of principle, and in the HBM4EU aligned studies, with the aim of improving the interpretation of exposure biomarker measurements and increasing the weight of evidence for exposure-health outcome associations in human observational studies, has almost been fully achieved.

The strategy for supporting the exposure-effect relationship, which is being applied in the HBM4EU aligned studies, as well as in some on-going HBM4EU case studies, and in certain existing European cohorts, has been presented during the workshop, including the strategy for the selection of biomarkers of effect for specific chemicals, health outcomes and exposure windows (e.g. biomarkers of reproductive effects associated with phthalate exposure in children/adolescents), as a proof of concept.

All WP14 partners have shown during this workshop, their work and effort in the measurement of biomarkers of both exposure and effect, to better understand the potential impact of environmental exposures on human health, one of the main HBM4EU research objectives. WP14 partners have interacted with other HBM4EU WPs (mainly WP8, WP10, WP11, WP13 and WP16), during these years, and the results presented in this last Workshop in Granada have demonstrated this connection.

During the workshop, the partners showed their preliminary results on the implementation of these biomarkers of effect within HBM4EU. Although HBM4EU is nearing its end, there are still some results to be explored. Fortunately, it is just a matter of statistical and data analysis.

The works presented at the workshop were divergent and not all of them were at the same level of development, impeding a more homogeneous scheme when presenting the different sections in terms of description of statistical tools of each of them. However, the variability and diversity of the activities developed in WP14 (from experimental to epidemiological studies) highlight the ultimate pre-WP14 objective, to study, select and implement biomarkers of toxicity-based effects in human biomonitoring programmes.

It has not been easy to reach this stage of the project. We had to face many doubts and questions, as is always the case in science when we enter unknown (or new) territories. This effort has to be continued by integrating the WP14 data into the new risk assessment.

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8 Annex: Workshop general Information

Target groups:

Mainly members of HBM4EU-WP14 as well as partners of other HBMB4EU-WPs (as WP9-WP10-WP13). All participants in HBM4EU were invited, as well as young researchers from the health and environment area of the organising institution (UGR).

Registration:

December 2021 – end of January 2022

Capacity:

Due to COVID's pandemic situation, it was necessary to change from the face-to-face modality (as in the two previous workshops) to the hybrid modality, both face-to-face and virtual.

Attendance:

There were more than 20 different scientific institutions from all over Europe participating in the Workshop. The meeting was attended by 30 researchers in person and by 45 researchers in virtual mode.

Funding of travels and accommodation:

Participants on-site themselves covered their travel and accommodation costs (previously allocated in the own HBM4EU budget).

Location, agenda and attending participants:

'School of Medicine, University of Granada'

This university center is located within the '*Parque Tecnológico de la Salud*' in front of the University Hospital "Clinico San Cecilio".

Address: Av. del Conocimiento, s/n

Phone: +34 958 24 10 00

Location: 18100 Granada, Spain

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Agenda

Granada 3rd Workshop HBM4EU WP14-WP13

Thursday, 10 February 2022 from 09:00 to 17:30
Friday, 11 February 2022 from 09:00 to 13:00
on site and virtual due to COVID-19

Day 1, Thursday, 10th February 2022

Time	Topic
09:00 - 09:15	Welcome (Marieta Fernández, WP14 - UGR) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome to the Workshop • Organisational issues of the meeting • Adoption of the agenda
	Implementation of HBM4EU effect biomarkers (1st and 2nd set)
09:15 - 09:45	Implementation of novel effect biomarkers in the 1 st and 2 nd occupational studies (Tiina Saantonen, Maria João Silva: INSA & FIOH)
09:45 - 10:15	Semi-targeted proteomic panel related with acrylamide exposure in Euromix (Lindeman Birgitte, NIPH)
10:15 - 10:45	Placenta biomarkers and birth outcomes (Claudia Gundacker, MUW)
10:45 - 11:15	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:15 - 11:45	Biomarkers of combined PFAS effect on human placentas (Eva Bonefeld-Jørgensen, AU)
11:45 - 12:25	Benzophenone-3: Systematic integrative review of the toxicological and epidemiological evidence with meta-analysis of HBM studies (Vicente Mustieles, Anna-Maria Andersson, Anne-Marie Vinggaard UGR-RegionH-DTU)
12:25 - 12:55	Effect Biomarkers in placenta from the PELAGIE cohort (Arthur David, Shereen D'Cruz, INSERM)
12:55 - 13:15	BDNF Validation and quality control (Marieta Fernandez, UGR)
13:15 - 14:30	<i>Lunch break</i>
	Experimental research to support human effect biomarkers
14:30 - 15:00	Transcriptomic responses of human HepaRG and lymphoid TK6 cells after exposure to selected genotoxic and non-genotoxic substances- in search for potential effect biomarkers applicable to HBM studies. (Katrin Kreuzer, BfR)
15:00 - 15:30	Experimental work done by CNRS to validate the effect biomarkers (Jean-Baptiste Fini, CNRS)

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Time	Topic
15:30 - 16:00	Experimental research on PFAS mechanisms and lipid metabolism (Jochem Louisse, RIKILT - RIVM)
16:00 -16:25	Synergies with WP13: updates and relevant activities (Ludek Blaha, MU)
16:25 – 16:50	<i>Coffee break</i>
16:50 -17:15	GENEIDA study assessing molecular biomarkers of brain damage (Antonio Hernández, EASP)
17:15 - 17:30	Brief summary of WP14 achievements Consensual WP14 inputs for the final HBM4EU conference

Day 2, Friday, 11th February 2022

Time	Topic
09:00 - 10:45	WP-10 exposure-effect analysis and pathways <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction (VITO – Eva) • PFASs and Metabolism/BMI in teenagers (KI – Tessa) • Phthalates/DINCH & FRs and Metabolism/BMI in children/teenagers (NIPH – Anteneh, Nina) • Phthalates/DINCH & PFASs and Sexual Maturation in teenagers (VITO – Sylvie) • Proposal overarching publication (VITO – Kirsten) • Phthalates/DINCH & PFASs, hormonal profile & kisspeptin in the FLEHS cohort (UGR – Andrea)
10:45 - 11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:00 -12:30	WP-10 exposure-effect analysis and pathways <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phthalates/DINCH & FRs and Neurodevelopment in children (UGR (CBCL)/EPIUD (WISC)) (UGR – Vicente / EPIUD – Fabio, Valentina) • Phthalates/DINCH (children) and PFASs (teenagers) and Asthma and allergy (VITO – Gudrun)
12:30 - 13:00	Conclusions and end of Workshop

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HBM4EU 3rd Granada Workshop 2022 participants				
	WP14 (UGR)	WP9	WP10	WP13 (MU)
Partners:	UGR	ISCIII	VITO	MU
Attending on-site	INSA		KI	
	FIOH		NIPH	
Attending virtually	NIPH		EPIUD	
	MUW		ISGlobal	
	AU		RegionH	
	DTU			
	INSERM			
	BfR			
	CNRS			
	RIKILT-RIVM			
	MU			
	EASP			
	VITO			
	UH			
	KU-Leuven			
	Swiss TPH			
	MOH-CY			
	IEM			
	NRCWE			
	ISCIII			
	EPIUD			
	NIOM			
	KI			
	LNS			

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Partners attending on-site:

Foreing partners:

Greet Shoeters (Pillar leader I) WP10, Eva Govarts WP10 leader, Kirsten Baken WP10, Argelia Castaño (Pillar leader II) WP9, Ludek Blaha WP13 leader

UGR team (WP14):

Marieta Fernández, Nicolás Olea, Carmen Freire, Juan Pedro Arrebola, Vicente Mustieles, Elena Salamanca, Andrea Rodríguez, Alicia Olivas, Iris Reina, Francisco Artacho, Francisco Peinado, María Sánchez Ríos, Luz Iribarne, Raquel Quesada, Cristina López, José Manuel Molina, Luis Fontana, Ana Isabel Álvarez Mercado, Fermín Sánchez, Olga Martínez, Matias Triviño

EASP team (WP14):

Marina Lacasaña, Antonio Hernández, Helena García, Antonio Gómez Martín, Clara Bermudez

